

D4.4 National Service Registry Prototype

Lead Partner:	CNR
Authors	L. Candela (CNR-ISTI), R. Cirillo (CNR-ISTI), L. Frosini (CNR-ISTI), L. Lelii (CNR-ISTI), F. Mangiacrapa (CNR-ISTI), F. Sinibaldi (CNR-ISTI), F. Antonio (CMCC), B. Chiavarini (CINECA), M. Lorini (GARR)
Version:	1.2
Status:	Final
Dissemination Level:	Public
Document Link:	10.5281/zenodo.7661068

Deliverable Abstract

National initiatives willing to systematically collect and present the service offerings of interest for their designated community are called to set up and operate a registry or catalogue of such services.

This brief report documents the working prototype of a National Service Registry developed by EOSC-Pillar. This prototype is characterised by two distinguishing features: (i) the development of the catalogue is the result of a collaborative oriented co-creation activity and (ii) conceived to be interoperable with the EOSC Catalogue.

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

This work by Parties of the EOSC-Pillar is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The EOSC-Pillar project is co-funded by the European Union Horizon 2020 programme under grant number 857650.

DELIVERY SLIP

<i>Date</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Partner/Activity</i>	<i>Date</i>
From:	L. Candela	CNR	
Moderated by:	F. Tanlongo	GARR	
Reviewed by:	S. Di Giorgio	GARR	
Approved by:	F. Galeazzi	GARR	

DOCUMENT LOG

<i>Issue</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Comment</i>	<i>Author</i>
v0.1	1 May 2021	First draft	L. Candela,
V0.8	1 Jun 2021	First complete version ready for review	L. Candela
V0.9	1 Jul 2021	Review comments received	S. Di Giorgio
V1.0	14 Jul 2021	Release version produced	L. Candela
V1.1	08 Feb 2023	Added Zenodo reference	F. Galeazzi
V1.2	05 May 2023	Fixed incomplete sentence in extended abstract	F. Galeazzi

TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
EOSC Provider	An EOSC Provider is an <i>EOSC System User</i> responsible for the provisioning of one or more <i>Resources to the EOSC</i> . <i>EOSC Providers</i> are organisations, a part of an organisation or a federation that manages and delivers Resources to End-Users. <i>EOSC Providers</i> can be: <i>Resource Providers, Service Providers, Data (Source) Providers, Service Developers, Research Infrastructures, Distributed Research Infrastructures, Resource Aggregators, Thematic Clouds, Regional Clouds</i> , etc.
EOSC Provider Profile	A set of information characterising an EOSC Provider.
EOSC Resource	An EOSC Resource is an asset made available by means of the <i>EOSC system</i> and according to the <i>EOSC Rules of Participation to EOSC End-Users</i> to perform a process useful to deliver value in the context of the EOSC. <i>EOSC Resources</i> include <i>Services, Data Sources</i> any other asset. A <i>Resource Profile</i> describes the information requested to onboard Resources into the EOSC Provider Portal
EOSC Resource Profile	A set of information characterising an EOSC Resource.
Virtual Research Environment	A web-based working environment conceived to provide a community of practice with services and data of interest
VRE	see Virtual Research Environment

Extended Abstract

Deliverable D4.4 is of type Demonstrator and the actual implementation of the deliverable is made available by <https://eosc-pillar.d4science.org/web/eoscpillaritserviceregistry/>

This brief document describes the major actions and decisions driving the development of the prototype.

The model underlying the prototype is reported in the picture below.

Figure 1. National / Thematic Service Registry Model

According to this model: (a) there are several stakeholders driving the development of a National / Thematic Service Registry from perspectives ranging from ownership up to implementation; (b) Service Providers are expected to be mobilized by the local initiative driving the development of the catalogue and to onboard their service into the local registry; (c) Resource onboarded locally are expected to contribute to the population of aggregative catalogues including the EOSC Catalogue thanks to an established agreement among the parties; (d) Prospective Service consumers are expected to discover services of interest by using the Registry / Catalogue they consider more convenient, be it the local registry or the overall EOSC Catalogue; (e) Every Registry / Catalogue is free to implement additional functionalities to provide its users with beyond the search and browse functionalities.

From the implementation point of view, we did not start from scratch, and selected services offered by the D4Science infrastructure (Assante et al. 2019a,b). In particular, D4Science makes it possible to easily create working environments dedicated to serve a designated community by providing them with the services of interest. Among other features, these working environments can be equipped with a customisable Catalogue to use for documenting and publishing items of interest thus to make the published items discoverable. The resulting environment is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. EOOSC-Pillar IT Service Registry Prototype

The working environment was configured to offer:

- A welcome page informing the users about the goal of the environment, the policies governing it, etc;
- A wiki containing detailed information about the procedures driving the development of the catalogue, e.g., guidelines for providers, eligibility criteria;
- The Registry authorised users can use to register or modify their services. Figure 3 showcases the user interface enacting the publishing of items. The same registry provides a rich search experience which allows for quick ‘Google-style’ keyword search as well as faceting by tags and browsing between the published items (services and providers). Figure 4 and Figure 5 showcase how the search and faceting options are offered;
- A social networking area that can be used by the members of the working environment to communicate. Apart from posts produced by human users, automatic posts are produced whenever a new item is published into the catalogue thus to inform the community;
- A members area where the user of the working environment get informed about their coworkers and can contact them;
- A management area where the managers of the overall environment control its functioning, e.g., decide who can be a member¹ and what members are allowed to publish items into the catalogue.

¹ The working environment is configured to enable a controlled membership, this implies that membership requests need to be approved. However, the catalogue content can be consumed also by guest users.

Figure 3. Service Registry Publishing Interface

Figure 4. Service Registry Search Interface

Figure 5. Service Registry Faceted Interface

A very important feature of the Registry enabling technology is the possibility to define the typologies of items that can be published by it and the metadata characterising every typology of item. In fact, catalogue item profiles can be defined by properly instantiating and exploiting the catalogue item model depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Data Catalogue Item Model

Every catalogue item:

- has a number of *common metadata* (independently of the typology of the item) including (i) a unique identifier, (ii) a title, (iii) a description, (iv) a number of tags, (v) a license, (vi) a visibility flag (to indicate whether the item is public, i.e. visible to everyone, or private, i.e. the item is visible to VRE members only), (vii) an author, (viii) a maintainer, and (ix) a typology. A typology adds additional metadata (see item-specific metadata);
- has a number of *item specific metadata*. Item specific metadata can be driven by a profile specifying a number of field specifications each characterising a metadata field by specifying: (i) its name, (ii) the mandatory flag (whether the field is mandatory or optional), (iii) the type of field values (i.e. String, Text, Boolean, Number, Geometry in GeoJSON, Time, Time interval, List of Times), (iv) the maximum number of occurrences (i.e. whether the field is repeatable or not), (v) any default value to be proposed, (vi) any accompanying note to facilitate the data entry, (vii) any controlled vocabulary to facilitate the selection of suitable values, (viii) any validator to check the inserted value correctness;
- has a number of specific *resources*, i.e., objects representing identifiable item payloads. Every resource has (i) an Identifier, (ii) the URL where the payload is stored, (iii) a name, (iv) a description, and (v) a format (e.g., CSV, XML).

Thanks to this characteristic, it was simple to configure the registry prototype to support the publishing of **EOSC Provider** and **EOSC Resource** items. In fact, in order to favour the interoperability between the registry prototype and the overall EOSC Catalogue it was decided to use the same set of information promoted by EOSC for its catalogue². Technical details on how to define profiles are reported in a dedicated wiki³.

The prototype was instantiated for the Italian community. In particular, representatives of the ICDI (Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure) initiative⁴ being partners in EOSC-Pillar have been mobilized to implemented the onboarding of their services by using the prototype.

The working environment was created in June 2020 yet it become fully operational in March 2021 where there was the official release of the EOSC profiles and it was possible to configure the prototype to use them and start the onboarding activity. Figure 7 reports the working sessions per month performed by the users of the working environment. A total of 4 EOSC Providers and 9 EOSC Resources have been onboarded into the prototype so far.

² EOSC Provider Profile is documented at <https://eosc-portal.eu/providers-documentation/eosc-provider-portal-provider-profile> while EOSC Resource Profile is documented at <https://eosc-portal.eu/providers-documentation/eosc-provider-portal-resource-profile>

³ https://wiki.gcube-system.org/gcube/GCat_Background#Metadata_Profile_v.3

⁴ <https://icdi.it/en/>

Figure 7. Service Registry Prototype Working Sessions

References

Assante, M. et al. (2019a) Enacting open science by D4Science. *Future Gener. Comput. Syst.* 101: 555-563 DOI: [10.1016/j.future.2019.05.063](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2019.05.063)

Assante, M. et al. (2019b) The gCube system: Delivering Virtual Research Environments as-a-Service. *Future Gener. Comput. Syst.* 95: 445-453 DOI: [10.1016/j.future.2018.10.035](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2018.10.035)